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Ecologies beyond the Human - Reimagining Nature-based Solutions through Relational and Multispecies Perspectives.

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Abstract:

Despite growing interest in Nature-based Solutions (NbS) and their promise to deliver social, economic, and environmental benefits for society, their human-centred utilitarian functionality raises questions about the adequacy and effectiveness of NbS. Now, with two-thirds of the world's population projected to live in cities by 2050, this trend could potentially accelerate biodiversity loss and wildlife habitat destruction, ultimately weakening our resilience against the looming planetary ecocide.

This paper offers a critique of Nature-based Solutions, focusing on their anthropocentric framing and explores how this can be reimagined through relational thinking and multispecies perspectives to envision resilient cities where all species thrive in harmony.

This study will employ a horizon scan approach for literature review, which allows for capturing the recent, fast-changing dynamics of NbS, urban planning, and more-than-human approaches. In particular, it examines recent developments at the intersection of NbS and multispecies justice to address human exceptionalism in urban planning and the built environment. We propose a moral shift that addresses ecological justice issues through transformative policy reform, plural knowledges and reimagined pedagogies, and more-than-human urban design.

Keywords: nature-based solutions, multispecies, more-than-human, urban planning, relational concepts

Main highlights:

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- Current Nature-based Solutions are predominantly anthropocentric and utilitarian
- Multispecies assemblages play a pivotal role in shaping the urban fabric
- Reorienting urban planning to include multispecies relationality can address human exceptionalism
- Integrating the ethics of care and kinship in cities can address ecological justice issues

1. Introduction

The constant tension between urban environmentalism and development in this era of Anthropocene raises fundamental questions about access, justice, and liveability in cities. Western culture has historically viewed nature as a separate entity that can be exploited for human benefit (Milstein et al., 2023), and though nature-based solutions (NbS) and ecosystem services acknowledge the role nature plays in planetary thriving, they are essentially anthropocentric. More-than-human perspectives hold potential for dissolving these binaries by recognising the agency and the complex web of transpecies encounters (Price and Chao, 2023).

Research over the years has evidenced how rising urbanisation impacts biodiversity, modifies landforms, and alters habitats (Godefroid and Koedam, 2003; Andersson, 2006; Concepción et al., 2015). Rapid urbanisation and the continued perpetuation of unsustainable construction practices in cities indicate the need to explore approaches that move beyond human-centric and utilitarian pathways (Kipar, 2024). The distinction of humans from nature, and the pervasive blueprinting that runs across NbS policy design, urban planning, and bureaucracy, have limited the scope of the field (Welden, Chausson and Melanidis, 2021).

This horizon scan literature review seeks to establish the correlation between NbS in urban planning, multispecies justice, and relational concepts. It will explore interdisciplinary intersections and synergies, assess potential for systems change, and investigate the appropriate scale for implementing more-than-human principles in urban settings.

2. Exploring the scope of NbS through Multispecies Approaches: A Horizon Scan

Unlike the traditional systematic reviews (Snyder, 2019), which follow a thorough yet rigid search algorithm to examine a particular research question over an extended period, this paper takes a horizon scan approach.

Multispecies approach within NbS, while relatively new, is a fast-evolving field of study not only within urban studies but across diverse disciplines. Since the effort is to find interlinkages across interdisciplinary fields and map potential converging approaches, predefined inclusion/exclusion criteria of a systematic review would be unsuitable. Instead, this review

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will employ a horizon scan method to identify plausible futures and identify potential challenges, weaving together emerging narratives from different disciplines to inform policy design, decision-making, education and urban planning practices.

Horizon scan (Schultz, 2006; Sutherland and Woodroof, 2009; Sutherland et al., 2014; Hines et al., 2019) allows broader, more flexible searches that extend beyond academic work. It captures early, fluid developments across disciplines and permits examining the subject through multiple dimensions, which adequately addresses the field's complexity and interdisciplinary nature.

Apart from databases like Google Scholar, the search methods included academic blogs, human rights, environmental and practice-related publications, and citation chaining. This review captures insights from disciplines like urban studies, geography, science and technology studies (STS), and environmental and conservation humanities.

The horizon scan positions NbS at the intersections of multispecies approaches and relational concepts, first by contextualising through urban morphology (section 2.1), then further exploring the potential of NbS through multispecies approaches and relational concepts (Sections 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4).

2.1. Urban Morphology and City Form

The causal relationships between industrialisation and urbanisation run deep and can be traced back through temporal shifts in urbanism. However, historians (Hohenberg, 1990; Meyer, 2000) have questioned whether a city was the product or the agent of industrial modernisation. Michael Hough (2002) has described how these values have put the urban landscape at odds with natural and social processes. Ontological studies also reflect how non-human species shape economic systems, as witnessed in the well-documented spice trade, which played a central part in colonial expansion and geopolitics (Morton and Timothy, 2006; Sullivan, 2017). There is clear evidence of industrialisation replacing coexistence with other species with mechanistic solutions designed for human benefits (McKinney, 2008; Fields, 2012), causing cities to become progressively divorced from nature in response to political forces, linear economic models, and evolving demographics.

Urban design studies are rapidly evolving in the quest to strike the right balance for just distribution and habitable conditions for all. This evolution spans from sustainable design (Crocker and Lehmann, 2013), biophilic architecture (Kellert, Heerwagen and Mador, 2011), regenerative design (Wahl, 2016), circular design (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2024), to now more transdisciplinary paradigms, like more-than-human design (Heitlinger et al., 2018), bio-integrated design (Cruz and Parker, 2022), and multispecies design (Grobman et al., 2023) — leading to a new paradigm of city forms that challenge the destructive 'capitalocene city' (Moore, 2017).

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Houston et al. (2018) and Franklin (2017) argue that a 'more-than-human city' can enhance response to the climate crisis and can provide diverse adaptive futures. However, to achieve this radical transformation, urban planning needs to study the deeper relational interactions with natural systems and other species. Roos (2017) endorses applying a design pattern language that recognises these nested systems and the complex web of human-nature interactions.

Centring eco-centric principles in urban planning is now recognised as the new frontier for addressing biodiversity conservation in cities. For instance, Biodiversity-sensitive urban Design (BSUDS) considers the multispecies entanglement in the functioning of the urban fabric (Fieuw, Foth and Caldwell, 2022), while landscape theory employs animal-aided design (AAD), which can enhance biodiversity in cities (Weisser and Hauck, 2017; Ocaña, 2025).

Jon, Guma and Simone (2024) advocate for a 'humanistic city', which, while situated in the entanglements of more-than-human assemblages, is constantly evolving through generative, spatio-temporal intra-actions.

For a city to thrive, it does not necessarily mean running with an anti-urban narrative. Hinchliffe and Whatmore (2008) reimagine urban inhabitants as not just more-than-humans but more-than-living beings in their vision for 'Living cities'. Wherein the complex assemblages that represent the urban ecology go beyond the contrived human-caused opportunities and barriers, but operate on affective means of becoming, i.e. the non-living entities together with human and non-human species animate to create a symbiotic habitat. The concept goes on to suggest 'ecology going urban and cities becoming ecological', urging humans to pay attention to the diversity of the urban-ecological attachment and interactions.

Robinson, Breed and Beckett (2024), through their model of 'Probiotic cities', drive the focus to the oft-neglected microbial species and the key role they play in the health of a city and its inhabitants. They advocate for blending microbial science and bio-integrated design, which essentially incorporates living organisms in human-made environments and enhances their functionality by leveraging their biological activities, to tackle urban challenges.

2.2. Examining the limitations and scope of Nature-based Solutions

2.2.1. Anthropocentrism in NbS

Nature-based Solutions are often criticised for their anthropocentric agenda (Lemes de Oliveira, 2025), which focuses on enhancing ecosystem services for humans. Rees and Doyon (2023) further criticise NbS for reproducing colonialism through power asymmetries, validly drawing attention to people involved in designing NbS frameworks and policies. If NbS perpetuates colonial systems and power structures while ignoring marginalised voices like the indigenous peoples, it will further accelerate the climate crisis (Indigenous Climate Action (ICA), 2021).

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To resolve the dichotomous debate of Human Vs Nature, the premise of the NbS approach needs to align with bioregionalism (Budoni and Ricci, 2020), as it establishes connections with living systems, recognises ecological boundaries and their agency, and defines the role humans play in cohabitation within the planetary limits.

Anthropocentrism in NbS should not be simplified through the purview of human exceptionalism, but rather examined through the lens of power and political inequities that have led to the looming ecological collapse (Rees and Doyon, 2023).

Though climate change impacts all species, the dilemma of non-human species is poorly represented in NbS interventions; hence, NbS should not be shaped solely by human intentionality. For instance, 'just green enough' for societal benefits would not work (Reed-Thryselius, 2023), widening the circle of actors and stakeholders through the relational and distributional networks could expand the impact of NbS (Welden, 2023).

2.2.2. A critical perspective on Environmental Strategies and NbS policy

To tackle the anthropocentrism of NbS, reimagining NbS to include more-than-human stakeholders can be pivotal — for instance, the urban greening NbS often aim at providing solutions for enhancing the urban habitat for humans (Ventura, Shwartz and Strubbe, 2025) creates a fallacy that humans can control nature and can decide or customise its outcomes and benefits.

Although there are strategies for increasing urban biodiversity, they are centred on prioritising certain species and their populations, as Palmer (2003) reiterates, without sufficiently acknowledging the relationality among all species. Research suggests that urban greening strategies and planning continue to reproduce inequities and injustice (Bragança, 2025).

There has been a growing discourse around granting rights to nature through 'rights of nature' and personhood (Pain and Pepper, 2021; Petel, 2025). However, if non-human species and ecosystem assets are granted personhood and become active stakeholders in NbS, how can their agency be ensured, and who advocates for them? Would questions like 'Who gains and who pays?' receive honest responses from humans? (McIntyre-Mills, 2021).

2.2.3. Expanding the boundaries of Justice in NbS

Despite the rising awareness of a skewed justice delivery, the imbalance of benefits and burdens persists, and there remains a vast ground to cover in terms of reimagining the system, its processes and operations, given the entrenched human-centredness. NbS participatory and democratic processes are recognised; however, these need to be advanced to enable interspecies communication (McKay, 2017) by enabling intergenerational capabilities for long-term impact (Pineda-Pinto et al., 2025).

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While efforts for socio-ecological justice have been embedded in NbS practice — through multi-level governance, diverse participation, and measures to evaluate just outcomes — they fail to address nuanced questions such as ‘justice for whom?’, ‘is it just enough?’, and ‘who decides that?’ (Wijisman and Berbés-Blázquez, 2022). Broadening the scope of representation in NbS within an urban context and blurring the set lines of representation in polity (Hinchliffe et al., 2005) would allow addressing these questions. Multispecies flourishing urges urban planners to embed fair representation, distribution and agency and emphasise co-existing and co-learning rather than transforming the other for human benefits. Raymond et al. (2025) emphasise how NbS can approach the awkward relationships with undesirable species like mosquitoes and slugs without intervening or transforming, but through new spatial imaginaries that transcend beyond thinking about and extend to thinking with other species - for instance, through art-based multispecies placemaking (Olsen, 2022).

2.3. Exploring Multispecies Perspectives

In recent years, multispecies studies have addressed anthropocentrism across sectors, while prioritising the freedom of other species and highlighting the capabilities and rights of non-humans, particularly within urban environments (Holmberg, 2022). This exploration can catalyse dismantling dualistic notions of Human Vs Nature (Hočevár, 2023) and embrace more relational ontologies (Riley, Jukes and Rautio, 2024).

2.3.1. Emergence of Multispecies

Multispecies studies are an evolving field that’s deeply rooted in moral concern for the heightening inhospitable conditions for non-human life. It urges acknowledging and understanding the complexities and interdependence of all species for mutual thriving. The critique of the relationship between materialism and human action originated in Karl Marx’s theory of the ‘metabolic rift’ (Franklin, 2017; Jon, Guma and Simone, 2024) and was expanded to include environmental concerns by John Bellamy Foster (1999). Posthumanism, feminism, and new materialism have been the theoretical underpinnings of multispecies research. Ethnographically, the domain has a long history, like Richard Grusin’s ‘The non-human turn’ (Grusin, 2015), James Bridle’s more nuanced exploration of more-than-human planetary intelligence in “Ways of Being” (Bridle, 2022), and Donna Haraway’s revolutionary feminist multispecies theory (Emel and Nirmal, 2021).

The term was first mentioned in 2008 in Donna Haraway’s book ‘When Species Meet’ (Haraway, 2023). Grounded in posthumanist thought, feminist and critical animal studies, and expanding into environmental studies and STS (Kirksey and Helmreich, 2010), multispecies justice (MSJ) strives to widen perspectives by including political, ethical, and social factors that influence more-than-human encounters (Celermajer et al., 2022).

While in recent years, urban geographers have increasingly recognised the non-human actors as central to the form, function, and evolution of a city (Hinchliffe et al., 2005; Gandy, 2014), anthropocentrism still shadows urban governance. A major barrier for multispecies acceptance is its sparse mention in urban politics and science, and the othering of non-

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humans as externalities (Franklin, 2017; Jon, 2020). The problem persists when there is no recognition of who the non-human actors are, whether they matter for the everyday functioning or even in the long-term survival.

To change this status quo requires recognising there is a problem with the human-centric ideals of developed cities and measuring their impact on the larger planetary health. Efforts like paleo-ecological data can help democratise representation in decision-making and help institutionalise MSJ (Gillespie, Penny and Hamilton, 2025). Whereas the open-ended digital project, Feral Atlas (Tsing et al., 2020), maps the ecological impact of human activities, while revealing the feral capacities of species that co-evolve through human interventions, potentially supporting the thriving of certain species.

2.3.2. Recognising MSJ potential for transforming NbS

From the NbS context, MSJ takes NbS beyond the realm of societal benefits and highlights more-than-human sociality, enabling all species to engage, function, and thrive in a space. Tailoring NbS through a multispecies approach would normalise co-existence with all life forms, counterbalance the technocratic interventional approach of NbS, and thereby embed long-term effectiveness (Pineda-Pinto, Frantzeskaki and Nygaard, 2022; Stanley et al., 2025).

The concept of ecological space links distributive justice and multispecies justice, establishing accountability for human use of ecological space (Raymond et al., 2025). While tools like the Green Factor tool ascertain healthier and higher biodiversity in urban areas, they can result in skewed spatial distribution as the tool overlooks interspecies concerns (Arcari, Probyn-Rapsey and Singer, 2021).

Pineda-Pinto et al. (2025) state that the capability approach (CA) can embed MSJ in NbS. Originally conceptualised by Amartya Sen (1988), CA emphasises processes — focusing on functioning rather than function. Martha Nussbaum (2011) further expanded the framework to include multispecies considerations through the 'Justice for Animals' theory.

2.3.3. The Relational dynamics of MSJ and NbS

NbS are often incompatible with complex and slow ecological processes and rapidly changing social dimensions (Lehmann et al., 2025). Questions about their longevity, cascading effects, beneficiaries, and fundamental purposes need to be prioritised. To restore human-nature connections, place-based knowledge of non-human life and its interdependencies is crucial for generating ecological relationality and empathy (Van Dooren and Rose, 2012). Hence, re-imagining NbS through relational concepts is important (Robertson, 2018).

As Massey (2013) and Ingold (2021) imply, when examining the dimensions of place and time, understanding humans' complex interrelationship with multispecies actors is crucial. Throughout history, the interplay of cultures and politics has created a messy network of flows and alliances and contributed to unsustainable urban spaces. Hence, place-making needs to be approached as an inclusive, ongoing and open-ended practice.

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When humans are detached and alienated from nature, they are less inclined to care for and protect non-human nature. Rather than viewing relationships through the pyramidal approach of distinction, the post-human feminist ontology encourages looking at humans as relational beings deeply connected to nature (Braidotti, 2017; Ceder, 2018).

Ludert et al. (2024) emphasise planetary ethics through empathy and care, and clarify that this can be achieved without decentering human needs but rather by expanding designers' capacities and fostering collective intelligence and capabilities. Whereas, based on ecological justice dimensions, Pineda-Pinot et al.'s (2022) 'Ecologically Just Cities' framework not only improves the multifunctionality of NbS but also dissolves the abstraction of justice issues.

2.4. Exploring Relational Concepts for aligning NbS and MSJ discourses

Recent scholarly literature increasingly advocates eco-economies that do not instrumentalise nature, drawing from neo-animist ontologies that prioritise relational and pluralistic NbS (Escobar, 2008; Arnould, 2022). Relational thinking emphasises processes, which entail understanding the processes at multiple scales across different temporal and spatial frames (Healey, 2006). For instance, taking into account the fast life of microbes and the slow growth of trees at the same time.

Exploring different concepts of relational thinking and their synergies could help develop an NbS framework that incorporates nested systems and their spatial and temporal connections while providing long-term benefits, as shown in Figure 1.

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Figure 1: Relational thinking models for expanding the potential of NbS

Authors Isaacs and Otruba, (2019), Aisher and Damodaran (2016), and Wilson (2019) have delved into the relationality of all species through Mary Louis Pratt's concept of 'contact zones' — spaces where species are biologically, culturally and politically intertwined. This approach does not demand altruism, but rather can work through relational concepts of conativity and conviviality. Philosopher Freya Mathews (2011) advocates leveraging conativity — the base impulse of living beings' to maintain and increase their existence — by 'weaving one's conative ends with the conative goals of others.'

Whereas Hinchliffe and Whatmore (2008) have proposed a framework of politics of conviviality (Figure 2) based on three theoretical impulses - the first is grounded in Nikolas Rose and James Tully's work on Political Agonism, which engages citizen capacities irrespective of their identity or alignment and works solely through the complex web of interactions. The second impulse is inspired by feminist philosopher Rosalyn Diprose's Corporeal generosity, theorised on thriving through relational associations with others. The third impulse is Cosmopolitics, a concept inspired by philosopher Isabelle Stengers, which emphasises on co-production of knowledge and the democratisation of expertise.

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people who shape and live in that neighbourhood. This approach can be further expanded through more-than-human perspectives.

3. Conclusion

The horizon scan identifies recognition, distribution, and procedural justice issues that extend beyond the human realm to include other species and the planet, recognises the entangled relationships of human and non-humans, and examines how NbS can leverage these ecological assemblages.

Recognitional factors can be addressed through plural knowledges that acknowledge Indigenous perspectives and other worldviews. While expanding the horizon of interspecies, inter-generational learning approaches, and the seventh generation principles (Syropoulos et al., 2024) can be transformative, we suggest a radical shift in education that encourages youth to reflect on existentialism and view humans as relational beings. Alternative pedagogies like embodied and transformative learning can be a promising approach; however, it will be crucial to avoid the selective representation of nature.

To address distributional issues, we emphasise that designing for more-than-human species should not be reduced to another urban design typology or a city form. Instead, it should be grounded in situated contexts and engage with the local ecological complexities and relationships. It can be applied through a fractal scale-linking approach that starts with a relational neighbourhood unit and expands to include more-than-human perspectives.

Since anthropocentrism stems not only from human exceptionalism but also from power inequalities within human-centric systems, dismantling these inequities would need new political configurations, ecological partnerships, plural knowledge and practices.

To tackle these procedural injustices, capacity building through multispecies partnerships (Tsing, 2015) can forge non-hierarchical, co-productive relationships between multispecies communities. We recommend developing an NbS Policy reform that foregrounds relationality, built on collective ownership, collaborative bureaucracy, and a more open-ended legislation.

While this horizon scan does not provide a structured NbS design framework, it includes building blocks grounded in reciprocity, care, and empathy — ones that recognise all species as kin within urban settings.

4. REFERENCES

AISHER, A. and DAMODARAN, V. (2016) Introduction: Human-nature Interactions through a Multispecies Lens. *Conservation and Society*, 14(4), p. 293.

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

- ANDERSSON, E. (2006) Urban Landscapes and Sustainable Cities. *Ecology and Society*, 11(1), [Online] Available from: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26267821> [Accessed 06/08/2025].
- ARCARI, P., PROBYN-RAPSEY, F. and SINGER, H. (2021) Where species don't meet: Invisibilized animals, urban nature and city limits. *Environment and Planning E: Nature and Space*, 4(3), pp. 940–965.
- ARNOULD, E.J. (2022) Ontology and circulation: towards an eco-economy of persons. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 38(1–2), pp. 71–97.
- BHABHA, H.K. and RUTHERFORD, J. (2006) Third Space. *Multitudes*, 26(3), pp. 95–107.
- BRAGANÇA, L.S. (2025) MULTISPECIES PROJECT: A Multispecies Approach to Communities in Urban Green Spaces in Times of the Anthropocene. In: LEAL FILHO, W. et al. (eds) *Composing Worlds: Humanities, Health and Wellbeing in the XXI Century Towards a More Sustainable World*. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, pp. 11–28.
- BRAIDOTTI, R. (2017) Critical Posthuman Knowledges. *South Atlantic Quarterly*, 116(1), pp. 83–96.
- BRIDLE, J. (2022) *Ways of Being: Animals, Plants, Machines: The Search for a Planetary Intelligence*. Penguin UK.
- BUDONI, A. and RICCI, L. (2020) Green And Blue Infrastructures As The Structure Of A Bioregion: The Case Of The Pontina Bioregion. *WIT Transactions on Ecology and the Environment*, 249, pp. 179–190.
- CEDER, S. (2018) *Towards a Posthuman Theory of Educational Relationality*. London: Routledge.
- CELERMAJER, D. et al. (2022) Multispecies justice: theories, challenges, and a research agenda for environmental politics. In: *Trajectories in Environmental Politics*. Routledge.
- CONCEPCIÓN, E.D. et al. (2015) Impacts of urbanisation on biodiversity: the role of species mobility, degree of specialisation and spatial scale. *Oikos*, 124(12), pp. 1571–1582.
- CREX COLLECTIVE and JICKLING, B. (2018) Why Wild Pedagogies? In: JICKLING, BOB et al. (eds) *Wild Pedagogies: Touchstones for Re-Negotiating Education and the Environment in the Anthropocene*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 1–22.
- CROCKER, R. and LEHMANN, S. (2013) *Motivating Change: Sustainable Design and Behaviour in the Built Environment*. Routledge.

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

- CRUZ, M. and PARKER, B. (2022) From Anthropocene to Biocene: Novel Bio-Integrated Design as a Means to Respond to the Current Biodiversity and Climate Crisis. In: *Design Studio Vol. 4: Working at the Intersection*. RIBA Publishing.
- ELLEN MACARTHUR FOUNDATION (2024) *Building Prosperity: Unlocking the potential of a nature-positive, circular economy for Europe*.
- EMEL, J. and NIRMAL, P. (2021) A feminist research agenda for multispecies justice. In: HOVORKA, A., MCCUBBIN, S. and VAN PATTER, L. (eds) *A Research Agenda for Animal Geographies*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- ESCOBAR, A. (2008) *Territories of Difference: Place, Movements, Life, Redes*. Duke University Press.
- FIELDS, G. (2012) Urbanization and the Transition from Agrarian to Industrial Society. *Berkeley Planning Journal*, 13(1), [Online] Available from: doi.org/10.5070/BP313113032 [Accessed 04/08/2025].
- FIEUW, W., FOTH, M. and CALDWELL, G.A. (2022) Towards a More-than-Human Approach to Smart and Sustainable Urban Development: Designing for Multispecies Justice. *Sustainability*, 14(2), p. 948.
- FISHER, K. and PARSONS, M. (2020) River Co-governance and Co-management in Aotearoa New Zealand: Enabling Indigenous Ways of Knowing and Being. *Transnational Environmental Law*, 9(3), pp. 455–480.
- FOSTER, J.B. (1999) Marx's Theory of Metabolic Rift: Classical Foundations for Environmental Sociology. *American Journal of Sociology*, 105(2), pp. 366–405.
- FRANKLIN, A. (2017) The more-than-human city. *The Sociological Review*, 65(2), pp. 202–217.
- GANDY, M. (2014) *The Fabric of Space: Water, Modernity, and the Urban Imagination*. MIT Press.
- GILLESPIE, J., PENNY, D. and HAMILTON, R. (2025) Time, justice, and urban nature: procedural barriers to multi-species flourishing. *npj Urban Sustainability*, 5(1), p. 17.
- GODEFROID, S. and KOEDAM, N. (2003) How important are large vs. small forest remnants for the conservation of the woodland flora in an urban context? *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 12(4), p. Pages 287-298.
- GROBMAN, Y.J. et al. (2023) Architectural Multispecies Building Design: Concepts, Challenges, and Design Process. *Sustainability*, 15(21), p. 15480.
- GRUSIN, R. (2015) *The Nonhuman Turn*. U of Minnesota Press.

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

- HAKIO, K. and MATTELMÄKI, T. (2019) Future Skills of Design for Sustainability: An Awareness-Based Co-Creation Approach. *Sustainability*, 11(19), p. 5247.
- HARAWAY, D. (2023) When Species Meet. In: *The Routledge International Handbook of More-than-Human Studies*. Routledge.
- HEALEY, P. (2006) Relational complexity and the imaginative power of strategic spatial planning¹. *European Planning Studies*, 14(4), pp. 525–546.
- HEITLINGER, S. et al. (2018) Avoiding ecocidal smart cities: participatory design for more-than-human futures. In: *Proceedings of the 15th Participatory Design Conference: Short Papers, Situated Actions, Workshops and Tutorial - Volume 2*. PDC '18. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, pp. 1–3.
- HINCHLIFFE, S. et al. (2005) Urban Wild Things: A Cosmopolitical Experiment. *Environment and Planning D: Society and Space*, 23(5), pp. 643–658.
- HINCHLIFFE, S. and WHATMORE, S. (2008) Living Cities: Towards a Politics of Conviviality. In: *Environment*. Routledge.
- HINES, P. et al. (2019) Scanning the horizon: a systematic literature review of methodologies. *BMJ open*, 9(5), p. e026764.
- HOČEVAR, M. (2023) Mapping the dualisms of nature/society and nature/culture in environmental sciences in view of the anthropocene. *Družboslovne razprave*, 39(104), pp. 21–47.
- HOHENBERG, P.M. (1990) *The City: Agent or Product of Urbanization*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- HOLMBERG, M. (2022) Beyond Anthropomorphism. *ACME: An International Journal for Critical Geographies*, pp. 172-187 Pages.
- HOUGH, M. (2002) *Cities and Natural Process*. London: Routledge.
- HOUSTON, D. et al. (2018) Make kin, not cities! Multispecies entanglements and 'becoming-world' in planning theory. *Planning Theory*, 17(2), pp. 190–212.
- INDIGENOUS CLIMATE ACTION (ICA) (2021) *The risks and threats of "nature-based climate solutions" for Indigenous Peoples*. Canada: Indigenous Climate Action.
- INGOLD, T. (2021) *Being Alive: Essays on Movement, Knowledge and Description*. London: Routledge.
- ISAACS, J.R. and OTRUBA, A. (2019) Guest Introduction: More-than-human contact zones. *Environment and Planning E: Nature and Space*, 2(4), pp. 697–711.
- JON, I. (2020) Deciphering posthumanism: Why and how it matters to urban planning in the Anthropocene. *Planning Theory*, 19(4), pp. 392–420.

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

- JON, I., GUMA, P. and SIMONE, A. (2024) "Humanistic" City in the Age of "Capitalocene". *Annals of the American Association of Geographers*, 114(1), pp. 107–122.
- KELLERT, S.R., HEERWAGEN, J. and MADOR, M. (2011) *Biophilic Design: The Theory, Science and Practice of Bringing Buildings to Life*. John Wiley & Sons.
- KIPAR, A.O. (2024) Smart Urban Resilience: From Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) to Nature-Positive Cities and Landscapes. *KEEP ON PLANNING FOR THE REAL WORLD. Climate Change calls for Nature-based Solutions and Smart Technologies. Proceedings of REAL CORP 2024, 29th International Conference on Urban Development, Regional Planning and Information Society*, pp. 769–774.
- KIRKSEY, S.E. and HELMREICH, S. (2010) The Emergence of Multispecies Ethnography. *Cultural Anthropology*, 25(4), pp. 545–576.
- LEHMANN, I. et al. (2025) Time in and for nature-based solutions. No quick fix solutions for complex ecological and social processes. *Nature-Based Solutions*, 7, p. 100219.
- LEMES DE OLIVEIRA, F. (2025) Nature in nature-based solutions in urban planning. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 256, p. 105282.
- LUDERT, E.P.M. et al. (2024) EXPLORING THE CONCEPT OF MULTIESPECIES DESIGN: PERSPECTIVES FROM MEXICO.
- MALLER, C. (2021) Re-orienting nature-based solutions with more-than-human thinking. *Cities*, 113, p. 103155.
- MASSEY, D. (2013) *Space, Place and Gender*. John Wiley & Sons.
- MATHEWS, F. (2011) Towards a Deeper Philosophy of Biomimicry. *Organization & Environment*, 24(4), pp. 364–387.
- MCINTYRE-MILLS, J.J. (2021) Stewardship: An Anthropocentric Misnomer? Rights, Responsibilities and Multispecies Relationships. In: MCINTYRE-MILLS, J.J. and CORCORAN-NANTES, Y. (eds) *From Polarisation to Multispecies Relationships: Re-Generation of the Commons in the Era of Mass Extinctions*. Singapore: Springer Nature, pp. 119–139.
- MCKAY, L.J. (2017) *Fauna Fiction: 'Interspecies Communication in Contemporary Literature' and 'The Animals in That Country'*. Melbourne: The University of Melbourne.
- MCKINNEY, M.L. (2008) Effects of urbanization on species richness: A review of plants and animals. *Urban Ecosystems*, 11(2), pp. 161–176.
- MEYER, J.R. (2000) *The Role of Industrial and Post-Industrial Cities in Economic Development / Joint Center for Housing Studies*. Graduate School of Design [and] John F. Kennedy School of Government: Harvard University.

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

- MHCLG (2025) *Plan for Neighbourhoods*. [Online] GOV.UK. Available from : <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/plan-for-neighbourhoods> [Accessed 11/08/25].
- MILSTEIN, T. et al. (2023) “Even I am a Part of Nature”: Unraveling the Human/Nature Binary to Enable Systems Change. *Environmental Communication*, 17(4), pp. 421–436.
- MOORE, J.W. (2017) The Capitalocene, Part I: on the nature and origins of our ecological crisis. *The Journal of Peasant Studies*, 44(3), pp. 594–630.
- MORTON, T. and TIMOTHY, M. (2006) *The Poetics of Spice: Romantic Consumerism and the Exotic*. Cambridge University Press.
- NUSSBAUM, M.C. (2011) The Capabilities Approach and Animal Entitlements. In: BEAUCHAMP, T.L. and FREY, R.G. (eds) *The Oxford Handbook of Animal Ethics*. Oxford University Press, p. 0.
- OCAÑA, J. (2025) *Post-Anthropocentric Urbanism: Designing Future Cities For More -Than-Human Worlds*. [Online] Urban Design Lab. Available from : <https://urbandesignlab.in/post-anthropocentric-urbanism-designing-future-cities-for-more-than-human-worlds/?srsltid=AfmBOoomkVOsBjzCRzezgQJsyHVMXAg04Sxodcu6eDs2pSiTN SNEcD6> [Accessed 17/08/25].
- DE OLIVEIRA, V.M. (2021) *Hospicing modernity: Facing humanity's wrongs and the implications for social activism*. North Atlantic Books.
- OLSEN, C.S. (2022) Co-Creation Beyond Humans: The Arts of Multispecies Placemaking | Article | Urban Planning. [Online] Available from: <https://www.cogitatiopress.com/urbanplanning/article/view/5288> [Accessed 03/08/2025].
- PAIN, N. and PEPPER, R. (2021) Can Personhood Protect the Environment? Affording Legal Rights to Nature. *Fordham International Law Journal*, 45(2), pp. 315–378.
- PALMER, C. (2003) Colonization, urbanization, and animals. *Philosophy & Geography*, 6(1), pp. 47–58.
- PETEL, M. (2025) *Beyond the critique of anthropocentrism: Rethinking the rights of nature*. [Online] OpenGlobalRights. Available from : <https://www.openglobalrights.org/beyond-the-critique-of-anthropocentrism-rethinking-the-rights-of-nature/> [Accessed 17/08/25].
- PINEDA-PINTO, M. et al. (2022) Planning Ecologically Just Cities: A Framework to Assess Ecological Injustice Hotspots for Targeted Urban Design and Planning of Nature-Based Solutions. *Urban Policy and Research*, 40(3), pp. 206–222.

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

- PINEDA-PINTO, M. et al. (2025) Realizing multispecies justice through a capability approach to promote nature-based solutions. *npj Urban Sustainability*, 5(1), p. 31.
- PINEDA-PINTO, M., FRANTZESKAKI, N. and NYGAARD, C.A. (2022) The potential of nature-based solutions to deliver ecologically just cities: Lessons for research and urban planning from a systematic literature review. *Ambio*, 51(1), pp. 167–182.
- PRICE, C. and CHAO, S. (2023) Multispecies, More-Than-Human, Nonhuman, Other-Than-Human: Reimagining idioms of animacy in an age of planetary unmaking. *Exchanges: The Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(2), pp. 177–193.
- RAYMOND, C.M. et al. (2025) Applying multispecies justice in nature-based solutions and urban sustainability planning: Tensions and prospects. *npj Urban Sustainability*, 5(1), pp. 1–9.
- REDVERS, N., GUZMÁN, C.A.F. and PARKES, M.W. (2023) Towards an educational praxis for planetary health: a call for transformative, inclusive, and integrative approaches for learning and relearning in the Anthropocene. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 7(1), pp. e77–e85.
- REED-THRYSELIUS, S. (2023) A Review of Environmental Gentrification Ills and the “Just Green Enough” Approach: on Achieving Justice, Sustainability, and Equity. *International Journal of Community Well-Being*, 6(4), pp. 411–422.
- REES, A. and DOYON, A. (2023) Unsettling NbS: A pathway towards shifting colonial power relations in nature-based solutions research and practice. *PLOS Climate*, 2(11), p. e0000307.
- RILEY, K., JUKES, S. and RAUTIO, P. (2024) Relational Ontologies and Multispecies Worlds: Transdisciplinary Possibilities for Environmental Education. *Australian Journal of Environmental Education*, 40(2), pp. 95–107.
- ROBERTSON, S.A. (2018) Rethinking relational ideas of place in more-than-human cities. *Geography Compass*, 12(4), p. e12367.
- ROBINSON, J.M., BREED, M.F. and BECKETT, R. (2024) Probiotic Cities: microbiome-integrated design for healthy urban ecosystems. *Trends in Biotechnology*, 42(8), pp. 942–945.
- ROOS, P. (2017) *Regenerative-adaptive design for coastal settlements: a pattern language approach to future resilience*. thesis. Deakin University.
- SCHULTZ, W.L. (2006) The cultural contradictions of managing change: using horizon scanning in an evidence-based policy context. *Foresight*, 8(4), pp. 3–12.
- SEN, A. (1988) *The Standard of Living: Lecture II. Lives and Capabilities*. Cambridge University Press.

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

- SINCLAIR, N. and ROBINSON, D. (2025) *The Relational Neighbourhood*. [Online] The Relational Neighbourhood. Available from : <https://relationshipsproject.org/the-relational-neighbourhood/> [Accessed 08/08/25].
- SNYDER, H. (2019) Literature review as a research methodology: An overview and guidelines. *Journal of Business Research*, 104, pp. 333–339.
- STANLEY, T. et al. (2025) Just nature recovery: A framework for centring multispecies and multi-dimensional justice in land management. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 164, p. 103992.
- SULLIVAN, S. (2017) What's ontology got to do with it? On nature and knowledge in a political ecology of the 'green economy'. *Journal of Political Ecology*, 24(1), [Online] Available from: doi.org/10.2458/v24i1.20802 [Accessed 06/08/2025].
- SUTHERLAND, W.J. et al. (2014) A horizon scan of global conservation issues for 2014. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 29(1), pp. 15–22.
- SUTHERLAND, W.J. and WOODROOF, H.J. (2009) The need for environmental horizon scanning. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 24(10), pp. 523–527.
- SYROPOULOS, S. et al. (2024).
- TILLMANN, T. (2020) Learning sustainability as an effect of disruption. *Environmental Education Research*, 26(1), pp. 14–26.
- TSING, A.L. et al. (2020) *Feral Atlas: The More-Than-Human Anthropocene*. Stanford University Press.
- TSING, A.L. (2015) *The Mushroom at the End of the World: On the Possibility of Life in Capitalist Ruins*. Princeton University Press.
- TYNAN, L. (2021) What is relationality? Indigenous knowledges, practices and responsibilities with kin. *cultural geographies*, 28(4), pp. 597–610.
- VAN DOOREN, T. and ROSE, D.B. (2012) Storied-places in a multispecies city. *Humanimalia*, 3(2), pp. 1–27.
- VENTURA, L., SHWARTZ, A. and STRUBBE, D. (2025) Scaling up nature-based solutions: dose-response effects of urban greening on avian biodiversity. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 392, p. 126834.
- WAHL, D.C. (2016) *Designing regenerative cultures*. Triarchy Press.
- WEISSER, W.W. and HAUCK, T.E. (2017).
- WELDEN, E.A. (2023) Conceptualising multispecies collaboration: Work, animal labour, and Nature-based Solutions. *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, 48(3), pp. 541–555.

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

- WELDEN, E.A., CHAUSSON, A. and MELANIDIS, M.S. (2021) Leveraging Nature-based Solutions for transformation: Reconnecting people and nature. *People and Nature*, 3(5), pp. 966–977.
- WIJSMAN, K. and BERBÉS-BLÁZQUEZ, M. (2022) What do we mean by justice in sustainability pathways? Commitments, dilemmas, and translations from theory to practice in nature-based solutions. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 136, pp. 377–386.
- WILSON, H.F. (2019) Contact zones: Multispecies scholarship through Imperial Eyes. *Environment and Planning E: Nature and Space*, 2(4), pp. 712–731.
- WOLF, M. (2000) The Third Space in Postcolonial Representation. In: SIMON, S. and ST-PIERRE, P. (eds) *Changing the Terms*. Translating in the Postcolonial Era. University of Ottawa Press, pp. 127–146.
- WRIGHT, K. (2014) Becoming-with. *Environmental Humanities*, 5(1), pp. 277–281.